

DIFFERENCES OF STRESS LEVELS AMONG ACCOUNTING JOBHOLDERS ACROSS ORGANIZATIONS IN QUEZON CITY

Marlon Dayto Andrada¹, Richelle Marie C. Verzosa¹, Daryl Ann N. Federipe¹, Princess Patricia C. Torres¹, Dr. Edna B. De Ocampo¹, Maria Korina Leslie P. Co²

¹College of Business Administration and Accountancy, AMA University, Quezon City, Philippines

²College of Professional and Graduate Studies, St. Joseph's College of Quezon City, Quezon City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the variations in stress levels among accounting jobholders across different organizational sectors which are accounting firms, corporate finance departments, and government offices in Commonwealth, Quezon City. It also examines whether stress differs between licensed and unlicensed practitioners. A total of ninety (90) accounting professionals participated in the study through purposive sampling. Stress levels were assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), and statistical analyses included frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, standard deviation, rank, One-Way ANOVA and Independent Samples t-Test to identify significant differences across groups. Findings reveal that government accounting jobholders exhibit the highest stress levels, accounting firm employees also report elevated stress while those in corporate finance showed comparatively lower stress. Regarding credential status, unlicensed accounting jobholders experienced higher stress than their licensed counterparts, particularly in relation to job security and unclear responsibilities. The study concludes that organizational type and licensure significantly influence workplace stress. These insights emphasize the need for sector-specific and credential-sensitive interventions to mitigate stress and support well-being of accounting jobholders.

Keywords: *Accounting Jobholder, Stress, Credential, Organization, Perceived Stress Scale, Licensure, Accounting Firm, Government, Corporate Finance*

INTRODUCTION

As the modern world continuously changes and improves, so does its economy. Thus, accounting jobholders may evolve to have new responsibilities and expectations that can significantly impact the well-being of those working in the field. Whether employed in accounting firms, corporate finance departments, or government agencies, accounting jobholders are increasingly faced with tight deadlines, complex regulatory demands, and shifting workplace dynamics (NeuroLaunch Editorial Team, 2024). Understanding Stress in Accounting Profession. NeuroLaunch. These factors can contribute to varying levels of stress, especially when considering differences in organizational structure and the credentials. In particular, the distinction between licensed and unlicensed accountants may influence the amount and type of pressure experienced, as licensure often comes with added responsibilities and higher performance expectations (Insogna CPA, n.d.).

While there may have been previous studies that explored stress in the accounting field, few have specifically examined how stress levels differ based on both organizational setting and licensure status (Sharma, 2022). Stress Management in Accounting & Workplace: Causes of Stress & Effective Techniques of Stress Reduction. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Commerce, Management & Social Science*, 5(4), 53–57. This gap is especially relevant in local contexts, where accountants operate in a range of different environments (Luo, et al., 2025). Occupational Burnout among Accountants: A Systematic Literature Review. *HRMARS*, 15(3). This issue is relevant even in other professions since workplace stress is now recognized as a major factor influencing job satisfaction, employee health, and staff turnover and without a clear understanding of who is most at risk and why, organizations may implement solutions that are too general or ineffective. There is a growing need to develop targeted support systems that account for differences in organizational roles and licensure.

Difference in stress levels in organizations may imply which needs more improvement in regards of their work flow or other things those other organizations managed to do better at, while if there is a huge difference in stress levels based in credential status may imply that there is a massive shift upon getting a license, more authority or autonomy may reduce stress overall (Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), 2018).

Research Questions

This study determined the differences of stress levels among licensed and unlicensed accounting jobholders across organizations in Commonwealth, Quezon City.

To obtain the essential data, this study answered the following research questions:

1. What type of organization does the respondents belong in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Accounting Firm;
 - 1.2. Corporate Finance; and
 - 1.3. Government?
2. What are the respondents' level of stress in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Work Content; and

- 2.1.1. Job Content
- 2.1.2. Workload and Work Pace=
- 2.1.3. Working Hours
- 2.1.4. Participation
- 2.1.5. Control
- 2.2. Work Context?
 - 2.2.1. Career Development, Status and Pay
 - 2.2.2. Role in the Organization
 - 2.2.3. Interpersonal Relationships
 - 2.2.4. Organizational Culture
 - 2.2.5. Work-Life Balance
- 3. What are the respondents' credentials in terms of the following:
 - 3.1 Licensed; and
 - 3.2 Unlicensed?
- 4. Does the level of stress among respondents significantly differ across different organizations?
- 5. Does the level of stress among respondents significantly differ based on their credentials?

METHODOLOGY

The research study utilizes the correlational research approach. This approach measures the direction of a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either of the variables. It aims to find out whether there is a positive correlation, negative correlation, or zero correlation making it the rationale why the researchers chose this method for the research study.

In order to achieve the researchers' aim, the research study employed a quantitative research design. The quantitative research design refers to systematic research that primarily focuses on quantifying data and applying statistical techniques to analyze the results, hence, well aligns with the research questions. In addition, this type of design emphasizes objectivity and reliability. In this study, the researchers will collect primary data from the respondents using quantitative research design and using correlational research approach to analyze the collected data. The focus shifted from work setup to credential status and organizational affiliation. The existing data remained valid and was realigned to match the new framework.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The research study targeted accounting jobholders in Commonwealth, Quezon City encompassing individuals engaged in various work arrangements, organizations, and credential status.

A stratified purposive sampling method was utilized to ensure representation across different work setups, but following a revision in the Statement of the Problem,

respondents were categorized by credential status (whether licensed and unlicensed), and organizational type (whether accounting firm, corporate finance department, and government office), which were determined based on job titles and reported work conditions during data collection. Initially, a total sample size of thirty (30) was considered, based on the Central Limit Theorem, which considers that sample means tend to a normal distribution when sample sizes are thirty (30) or larger. However, upon further consultation, the statistician recommended increasing the sample size to thirty respondents per work arrangement category to ensure sufficient data for meaningful analysis.

Description of Respondents

The research study's respondents were selected within the vicinity of Commonwealth, Quezon City. It targets jobholders working in the accounting field, whether licensed or unlicensed across different types of organization such as accounting firms, corporate finance departments, and government offices.

The respondents are 18 to 65 years old working as an accounting job holder for one year or more and working in onsite, remote, and hybrid setup within the vicinity but became not the focus after revision.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire is a structured set of written questions designed to collect specific information from a target group of respondents (Hassan, 2025). It typically consists of both demographic and content-related questions. Survey questionnaires are commonly administered through paper forms, online platforms, or interviews, and they aim to ensure consistency and comparability across all participants. Conversely, a Google Form is a free online tool developed by Google in 2012 that allows users to create customizable forms for collecting data and is widely used in education, research, and business for its simplicity, accessibility, and real-time data tracking. It offers various question types such as multiple choice, short answer, checkboxes, and dropdowns. Google Forms automatically stores responses in a connected Google Sheet for easy analysis.

The researchers of this study constructed a survey questionnaire used to gather quantitative data on perceptions in a systematic manner. The survey questionnaire was constructed using closed-ended questions to ensure efficiency in providing the researchers with quantitative data and reduce the amount of time spent of the respondents completing the survey questionnaire. The survey questionnaire was formed and distributed through Google Forms.

The survey questionnaire is divided into three (3) main sections. The sections being addressed in the survey questionnaire are respectively the respondents' demographic profile, assessment of the work setup, and levels of work-related stress. The first section seeks to gather demographic profiles of the respondents asking four questions linking to

their (1) age, (2) job tenure as an accounting jobholder, (3) job title, and (4) current work setup.

Table 1: Examples of Likert Scales

Response Set	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Quality	Very poor	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent
Intensity	None	Very mild	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Agreement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Approval	Strongly disapprove	Disapprove	Neutral	Approve	Strongly approve
Awareness	Not at all aware	Slightly aware	Moderately aware	Very aware	Extremely aware
Importance	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Familiarity	Not at all familiar	Slightly familiar	Moderately familiar	Very familiar	Extremely familiar
Satisfaction	Not at all satisfied	Slightly satisfied	Moderately satisfied	Very satisfied	Completely satisfied
Performance	Far below standards	Below standards	Meets standards	Above standards	Far above standards

The second section of the survey questionnaire employs a Likert Scale to quantify the respondents' assessment of the work setup namely onsite, remote, and hybrid as the independent variable. Each independent variable consists of five questions relating to (1) work arrangement, (2) commute and travel, (3) cost-effectiveness, (4) boundary management, and (5) technology and tools. The third and last section of the survey questionnaire also employs a Likert Scale to quantify the respondents' level of stress on work content and work context as the dependent variables. The dependent variable work content consists of five questions relating to (1) job content, (2) workload and work pace, (3) working hours, (4) participation, and (5) control; while the dependent variable work context consists of five questions relating to (1) career development, status and pay, (2) role in the organization, (3) interpersonal relationships, (4) organizational culture, and (5) work-life balance.

To measure the respondents' degree of agreement, the answers for the second and third section used a 6-Point Likert Scale shown in the table below:

Table 2: 6-Point Likert Scale

Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
(6)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)

Comprehensive testing procedures were done before the final distribution of the questionnaires to guarantee the research instrument's validity and reliability. The contents of the questionnaire underwent an evaluation to establish its validity. To establish the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha was used to determine the reliability of the survey questionnaire. The researchers secured a Certificate of Validation and Certificate of Reliability of the Survey Questionnaire to be used in Data Gathering.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers started the study by defining the aim of the research study, which is to determine if there is a significant relationship between the respondents' assessment of work setup and level of stress. The researchers then chose the type of data and methods needed to answer the research question, which is to collect primary data from the respondents using quantitative research design and using correlational research approach to analyze the collected data. Subsequently, the researchers constructed a standardized research instrument, which is a PSS-10 survey questionnaire. The research instrument then underwent comprehensive testing procedures by a statistician to guarantee its validity and reliability. The researchers consulted with the research adviser and provided the adviser with the documents issued by the statistician. With the approval of the research adviser, the researchers were then able to have a signal to proceed in conducting the survey.

As part of the scope of the research study, the respondents are accounting jobholders or individuals that work and hold an accounting job title. Using the Central Limit Theorem, the research study has a sample size of thirty (30) respondents which is considered to be sufficiently large. The research study has thirty (30) respondents for each independent variable – onsite, remote, and hybrid work setup – totaling to ninety (90) respondents. The survey questionnaire constructed through Google Form was given to the study's respondents within the vicinity of Commonwealth, Quezon City. The data gathering was administered by the researchers face-to-face and online with the respondents. The Google Form is standardized to all respondents. The researchers started the survey by introducing themselves and explaining their purpose with the prepared cover letter entitled Letter to the Respondents. The cover letter shown in the very first part of the Google Form also states that in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all responses gathered will be kept confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes only. The respondents have to tick the box that states "I agree to participate and take this survey." before they proceed. The researchers explained briefly the three sections of the survey questionnaire that contains: four (4) demographic profile related questions, and a total of fifteen (15) closed-ended questions that are answerable by a 6-Point Likert Scale. The respondents then proceeded in answering and completing the survey questionnaire. The Google Form automatically stored each completed response in a connected Google Sheet (similarly to a Microsoft Excel).

The data collection process started with setting the original research goal, which initially aimed to evaluate the relationship between work setup and stress levels among accounting jobholders. After the research defense and revisions to the Statement of the

Problem and hypotheses, the study's focus turned to comparing stress levels across different types of organization namely accounting firm, corporate finance, and government and between licensed and unlicensed accounting jobholders. Even though the research direction changed, the original data set was still valid and relevant since the responses captured the key variables needed for the new framework. The standardized format ensured consistency in data collection across all respondents, allowing for valid comparative analysis that aligned with the revised research objectives.

The respondents included accounting jobholders working in Commonwealth, Quezon City. While the researchers originally planned to verify organizational affiliation using email identification, technical issues with the Google Forms system led to not recording the email addresses so instead, respondents were later reclassified based on the revised independent variables (type of organization and credential status) by cross-referencing job titles, work setup and time recorded. The researchers were able to retrace the type of organization via time submission recorded and work setup in the data, while the job title was utilized to classify licensed and unlicensed accounting jobholders. Data that became irrelevant after the revisions in the Statement of the Problem were removed before giving the set of data to the statistician for analysis.

Analysis of Data

To interpret the data gathered according to the objectives of the study, the researchers utilized the following statistical tools: frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, standard deviation, rank, One-Way ANOVA and Independent Samples t-Test.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This mathematical tool shows the proportion of responses for each question by majority or minority. This tool was used to find out the frequency and percentage of all responses from the checklist part of the questionnaire, which includes the demographic profile of the respondents. The formula is as follows:

$$\% = (F / N) \times 100$$

Where:

%	=	Computed Percentage Distribution
F	=	Observed Frequency of Responses
N	=	Total Number of Respondents
100	=	Constant Value

Weighted Mean. This is the mean of the ungrouped data, computed as the sum of the product of the frequency and the unit weight divided by the number of the respondents (N). It is a value used to represent a set of numerical data. The weighted mean is used to determine the average assessment of the respondents regarding work setup and level of stress. The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum f_j w_i}{N}$$

Where:

WM	=	Weighted Mean
W_i	=	Weight Assigned
f_i	=	Frequency of each Response Option
$\sum f_j w_i$	=	Summation of the Weighted Frequencies
N	=	Total Number of Respondents

Standard Deviation. This mathematical tool shows the measure of how spread out or dispersed the values in a dataset are around the mean (average). The formula is:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

Where:

s	=	Sample Standard Deviation
n	=	Number of Observations
x_i	=	Each Individual Value
\bar{x}	=	Sample Mean
$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	=	Squared Difference between Each Individual Value and the Sample Mean
\sum	=	Summation of all the Squared Differences

Rank. This tool was used to show the order of individual stress indicator items by mean score to identify the most to least prominent stress indicator. Rank numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 were used.

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{s_p^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}}$$

One-Way ANOVA. This is a statistical test used to determine whether there are statistically significant differences between the means of three or more independent (unrelated) groups. In this study, it was used to test the null hypothesis on the differences of stress levels between accounting firms, corporate finance departments, and government offices. The formula for calculating the One-Way ANOVA is:

Table 3: One-Way ANOVA Formula

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares (MS)	F
Within	$SSW = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=1}^l (X - \bar{X}_j)^2$	$df_w = k - 1$	$MSW = \frac{SSW}{df_w}$	$F = \frac{MSB}{MSW}$
Between	$SSB = \sum_{j=1}^k (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X})^2$	$df_b = n - k$	$MSB = \frac{SSB}{df_b}$	
Total	$SST = \sum_{j=1}^n (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X})^2$	$df_t = n - 1$		

Where:

- F = F-ratio
- MSB = Mean Sum of Squares Between the Groups
- MSW = Mean Sum of Squares Within the Groups
- df = Degrees of Freedom
- SSB = Sum of Squares Between the Groups
- SSW = Sum of Squares Within the Groups
- SST = Sum of Squares Total

Independent Samples t-Test. This is a statistical test used to determine whether there are statistically significant differences between the means of two independent (unrelated) groups. In this study, it was used to test the null hypothesis on the differences of stress levels between licensed and unlicensed accounting jobholders. The formula for calculating the Independent Samples t-Test is:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{s_p^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}}$$

Where:

- t = t-ratio
- \bar{x}_1 = Sample Mean of group 1
- \bar{x}_2 = Sample Mean of group 2
- n_1, n_2 = Sample Sizes
- s_2 = Pooled Variance

The following scale was used to interpret the degree of stress in the research study:

Table 4: Degree of Stress Interpretation Scale

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretation	Stress Level
5.50 – 6.00	Very High Stress	Very High
4.50 – 5.49	High Stress	High
3.50 – 4.49	Moderate Stress	Moderate
2.50 – 3.49	Low Stress	Low
1.50 – 2.49	Very Low Stress	Very Low
1.00 – 1.49	No Significant Stress	Minimal

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Discussion of Results for Research Question 1

What type of organization does the respondents belong in terms of the following:

Table 5: Respondents' Organizational Type

Type of Organization	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Accounting Firm	20	22.22
Corporate Finance	40	44.44
Government	30	33.33
Total	90	100.00

Table 5 presents the distribution of accounting jobholders across different industries in Commonwealth, Quezon City. Out of all the respondents, 44.44% (n=40) are working in Corporate Finance, making it the most common industry for accounting jobholders in the area. This suggests that a large portion of accounting jobholders are engaged in private sector roles such as financial planning, budgeting, and analysis within corporations. While 33.33% (n=30) are employed in Government institutions. This indicates a significant representation of accountants in the public sector, possibly involved in regulatory, auditing, or budget management roles for government agencies. Lastly, 22.22% (n=20) are working in Accounting Firms, the smallest group among the three. These may include professionals involved in auditing, tax services, and consultancy, typically in public practice. The data shows a strong presence of accounting jobholders in corporate and government sectors, with fewer in traditional accounting firms. This may reflect broader

trends in employment preferences, availability of opportunities, or the scope of services demanded in the area.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 2

What are the respondents' level of stress in terms of the following:

Table 6. Respondents' Level of Stress in terms of Work Content

Work Content	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION	RANK
I am experiencing monotony, understimulation, meaningless of tasks, and lack of variety because of my work setup. <i>(job content)</i>	2.51	1.25	Somewhat Disagree	2
I am experiencing too much or too little workload to do, and work under time pressure because of my work setup. <i>(workload and work pace)</i>	2.63	1.34	Somewhat Disagree	1
I am experiencing strict or inflexible, long and unsocial, unpredictable, and badly designed shift systems because of my work setup. <i>(working hours)</i>	2.30	1.16	Disagree	3
I am experiencing lack of participation in decision-making because of my work setup. <i>(participation)</i>	2.18	1.01	Disagree	5

I am experiencing lack of control over work processes, pace, hours, methods, and the work environment because of my work setup. (<i>control</i>)	2.24	1.15	Disagree	4
Composite Mean	2.37	1.00	Very Low	

Mean Score Range | Verbal Interpretation - Stress Level
 5.50-6.00 Very High Stress - Very High; 4.50-5.49 High Stress - High; 3.50-4.49 Moderate Stress - Stress; 2.50-3.49 Low Stress - Low; 1.50-2.49 Very Low Stress - Very Low; 1.00-1.82 No Significant Stress – Minimal

This table presents the mean ratings, standard deviations, and verbal interpretations of respondents perceived stress related to Work Content dimensions under their current work setup. Each item was rated using a 6-point Likert scale, where higher scores indicate greater perceived stress.

Based on the results, the respondents reported very low levels of work-related stress in terms of work content under their current job setup, as reflected by the composite mean of 2.37. Among the five indicators, the highest source of stress was related to workload and work pace (mean = 2.63), suggesting that some employees occasionally feel overwhelmed or pressured by the amount or timing of tasks, though the overall agreement remains low. This was followed by job content (mean = 2.51), indicating mild concerns about monotony or lack of task variety. Meanwhile, lower stress levels were observed in terms of working hours (mean = 2.30), control over work processes (mean = 2.24), and participation in decision-making (mean = 2.18), suggesting that respondents generally do not feel burdened by inflexible schedules, lack of autonomy, or exclusion from workplace decisions. Overall, the findings reveal that the respondents experience minimal to very low stress related to the content and structure of their work.

Table 7: Respondents' Level of Stress in terms of Work Context

Work Context	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION	RANK
I am experiencing job insecurity, lack of promotion opportunities, under- or over-promotion, work of low social value, piece rate payment schemes, unclear or unfair performance evaluation systems, and being over- or under-skilled for a job because of my work setup. (<i>career development, status and pay</i>)	2.38	1.26	Disagree	1

I am experiencing unclear roles and conflicting roles in the organization because of my work setup. (<i>role in the organization</i>)	2.00	1.03	Disagree	5
I am experiencing inadequate, inconsiderate or unsupportive supervision, poor relationships with colleagues, bullying/harassment and violence, and isolated or solitary work because of my work setup. (<i>interpersonal relationships</i>)	2.11	1.23	Disagree	3
I am experiencing poor communication, poor leadership, lack of behavioral rule, and lack of clarity about organizational objectives, structures and strategies because of my work setup. (<i>organizational culture</i>)	2.06	1.02	Disagree	4
I am experiencing conflicting demands of work and home, lack of support for domestic problems at work, lack of support for work problems at home, and lack of organizational rules and policies to support	2.22	1.14	Disagree	2
work-life balance because of my work setup. (<i>work-life balance</i>)				
Composite Mean	2.15	0.95	Very Low	

Mean Score Range | Verbal Interpretation - Stress Level
5.50-6.00 Very High Stress - Very High; 4.50-5.49 High Stress - High; 3.50-4.49 Moderate Stress - Stress; 2.50-3.49 Low Stress - Low; 1.50-2.49 Very Low Stress - Very Low; 1.00-1.82 No Significant Stress - Minimal

Table 7 presents respondents perceived levels of stress related to work context, with a composite mean of 2.15, interpreted as very low stress. Among the five dimensions assessed, the highest-rated stressor was career development, status, and pay (mean = 2.38), indicating mild concerns regarding job security, promotion opportunities, or fair evaluation systems, though respondents generally disagreed that these were major issues. This was followed by work-life balance (mean = 2.22), suggesting some

employees experience occasional difficulty balancing personal and professional responsibilities. The remaining aspects interpersonal relationships (mean = 2.11), organizational culture (mean = 2.06), and the worker's role in the organization (mean = 2.00) all showed consistently low stress levels, indicating that respondents feel generally supported by colleagues, understand their roles, and perceive clarity in organizational leadership and communication. Overall, the results suggest that respondents experience minimal to very low stress from their work environment or context.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 3

What are the respondents' credentials in terms of the following:

Table 8: Respondents' Credential Status

Credential	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Licensed	44	48.89
Unlicensed	46	51.11
Total	90	100.00

Table 8 shows the distribution of respondents based on their professional credentials. Out of the total respondents, 51.11% (n=46) are unlicensed, while 48.89% (n=44) are licensed. This indicates a relatively balanced composition, with a slightly higher number of unlicensed individuals. The nearly equal distribution suggests that both licensed and unlicensed accounting jobholders are well represented in the sample, which could provide a comprehensive view of the workforce in terms of qualifications and licensure status.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 4

Does the level of stress among respondents significantly differ across different organizations?

Table 9: Significant Difference between the Accounting Jobholders' Stress Levels and Organizations

Type of Organization	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	P-VALUE
Accounting Firm	2.24	0.95	<0.001
Corporate Finance	1.98	0.68	
Government	2.99	1.11	

Table 9 presents the mean stress levels, standard deviations, and p-value comparing job stress across different organizations: Accounting Firm, Corporate Finance, and Government.

Respondents working in the Government sector reported the highest stress levels, with a mean score of **2.99 (SD = 1.11)**, approaching the moderate range of the 6-point Likert scale. This suggests that government accounting jobholders are experiencing relatively greater work-related stress compared to their counterparts in other sectors. Accounting Firms followed with a mean stress score of **2.24 (SD = 0.95)**, indicating very low stress, though still higher than the stress reported in Corporate Finance. The lowest stress level was observed in the Corporate Finance sector, with a mean of **1.98 (SD = 0.68)**, falling into the very low stress category. The p-value (**<0.001**) indicates that the differences in stress levels across industries are statistically significant, meaning that the variation in stress scores is unlikely due to chance. Therefore, the industry of employment appears to have a significant effect on perceived stress levels among accounting jobholders.

Ajibade (2014) found that job stress levels vary significantly depending on the organizational context, with public sector employees often reporting higher stress due to bureaucratic structure, rigid policies, and slower decision-making processes, compared to their private-sector counterparts. The researchers noted that government workers frequently experience role ambiguity, work overload, and limited career advancement, contributing to higher stress levels.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 5

Does the level of stress among respondents significantly differ based on their credentials?

Table 10: Significant Difference between the Accounting Jobholders' Stress Levels and Credentials

Credential	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	P-VALUE
Licensed	2.05	0.96	0.002
Unlicensed	2.68	0.95	

Based on the data, licensed respondents have a mean stress level of **(SD = 0.96)**, while unlicensed respondents report a higher mean stress level of **2.68 (SD = 0.95)**. The p-value of **0.002** is statistically significant, indicating a meaningful difference in stress levels between the two groups.

This result suggests that unlicensed professionals experience significantly higher levels of stress compared to licensed individuals. This may be attributed to factors such as job insecurity, limited career advancement opportunities, and lower professional recognition.

These findings are supported by previous studies, such as those by Naidu and Olivier (2025) and Kutebayev et al. (2024), which emphasize the heightened pressure experienced by less experienced or non-credentialed accountants due to tight deadlines, unclear roles, and financial instability. In contrast, licensed accountants, despite handling complex tasks and facing high expectations, appear to manage stress more effectively, possibly due to greater professional recognition, institutional support, and clearer career paths. As shown in the work of Baluran and Palic (2025), licensed professionals may benefit from stress management resources and seniority within their organizations.

Overall, the data reinforces the idea that credential status significantly influences stress levels among accounting jobholders, highlighting the need for targeted support, especially for unlicensed staff in high-pressure environments like Commonwealth, Quezon City.

Conclusions

Accounting jobholders working within Commonwealth, Quezon City generally experience low overall job stress in relation to both their job responsibilities and workplace environment. Nonetheless, stress levels are not evenly distributed among all employees. Those working in government positions and those lacking professional licensure tend to report higher levels of stress, particularly concerning career advancement opportunities, workload demands, and the balance between work and personal life.

These findings highlight the importance of clear career progression paths, professional qualifications, and adaptable organizational practices as key factors that help reduce occupational stress. To maintain overall low stress levels and effectively address areas with heightened pressure, it is advisable to implement ongoing stress assessments and specific measures such as encouraging professional certification, optimizing workload management, and enhancing promotion and support frameworks.

Recommendations

Grounded in the results of the study, possible improvements and directions for future action or research in the relevant field are the following:

1. Strengthen career development and licensure support. Government institutions and employers should improve promotion systems, provide training and mentorship, and support accounting professionals in pursuing licensure through review assistance, subsidies, or flexible schedules.
2. Improve workload management and work-life balance. Organizations should regularly assess task distribution, reduce excessive workloads during peak periods, adopt efficiency tools, promote flexible work arrangements and proper use of leave benefits.
3. Sustain employee well-being through supportive workplace programs. Employers and stakeholders should foster transparent communication, maintain a positive

organizational culture, and expand mental health awareness, stress management initiatives, and early burnout prevention programs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to participating in any data collection activities, all participants were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and any potential risks or benefits. Participants provided informed consent voluntarily and were assured of their anonymity and confidentiality. The confidentiality of participants' personal information and responses was strictly maintained throughout the research process. All data collected were anonymized and stored securely to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure. The research was conducted with honesty, integrity, and objectivity, without any bias or conflict of interest. The findings and conclusions presented in the study accurately reflect the data collected and are not influenced by any external factors.

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